

INFLUENCE OF IRREGULARITY OF LAND PLOTS ON THE STABILITY OF OPERATION OF AGRICULTURAL MACHINES

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In cotton growing, field irregularities reduce the efficiency of using engine power and tractor traction [1]. At the same time, the speed of the machine decreases and its vertical vibrations increase.

Elements of the micro-relief significantly reduce the stability of the tractor movement. The boundaries of dynamic stability when overcoming obstacles in the form of lugs and cavities are reduced to 40-60% of the boundaries of static stability [2, 3]. The main reason for the occurrence of transverse waves in irrigated lots is the dynamic effect of impacts of fast-moving cotton machines on poorly planned and not planned fields. Any slight irregularity of the field forms an initial push and thereby determines the beginning of wave formation. Subsequent movements, repeating this process, already destroy the surface of the field, squeezing the soil at the points of greatest stress, fixing the indentations and elevations in the form of transverse waves. In unplanned areas, when the tractor unit oscillates, which arises additional stress in the parts, loosening the fasteners, accelerating the wear, breakdowns and accidents of machines. In addition, in such fields, maintenance personnel work with high stress and become very tired.

With the increase in the speed of movement of tractor units and the increase in the grasp width, the requirements for the condition of the field surface increase, as in this case, in poorly planned fields the agricultural-technical performance of all machines and units decreases sharply. Field irregularities lead to the significant increase in the movement path of the units, as well as increase in energy consumption [3].

The article is based on the results of generalization, analysis, expert assessment of experience in designing reclamation machines, their operation according to the generally accepted classical methodology.

On an uneven, lumpy field, with open and double furrows and tubercles, aggregates cannot move at a sufficiently high speed due to strong push and impacts.

Let the wheel (fig 2.1.) moving with the forward speed ϑ , m/s, meets an obstacle with h height, in m. At the time of the wheel meeting with obstacle there is an impact, lasting Δt seconds. When the wheel rolls over the obstacle, the amount of movement increases by the amount

$$\Delta m \vartheta = m \cdot \vartheta \cdot \operatorname{tg} \alpha$$

until the wheel rises to height h . Hence, using the basic equation of dynamics, we determine the force:

$$P = \frac{\Delta m \cdot \vartheta}{\Delta t} = m \cdot \operatorname{tg} \alpha \cdot \frac{\vartheta}{\Delta t},$$

where m – reciprocating mass of the wheel, kg.

It is known that for soil, as for a complex body having the properties of elasticity, plasticity and hardness, the value of deformation can be assumed proportional to the speed and time of impact, i.e.

$$a = \vartheta \cdot \Delta t, \quad \Delta t = \frac{a}{\vartheta},$$

where a – the coefficient of proportionality determining duration of impact and characterizing total resilient (elastic) properties of running gear of the tractor and the soil. Then

$$P = m \vartheta^2 \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha}{a}.$$

As can be seen, this force is proportional to the square of the speed; the higher the obstacle the greater is force, and the smaller the greater the rolling radius.

The impact force will be greatest for the unit with a stiffer suspension and rim, and the least for the unit with an elastic suspension and on pneumatic tires. Soil condition also matters. The more plastic the soil, the shorter the impact time depends on the speed. Replacing in the above formula the value (a) equal to $\Delta t \cdot \vartheta$ we obtain the value of the force when moving the machine on plastic soil.

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